

CAMPUS WRITERS' SHARED EXPERIENCES IN USING AI-POWERED ENGLISH WRITING TOOL: A HERMENEUTIC PHENOMENOLOGICAL APPROACH

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Campus Writers' Shared Experiences in Using AI-Powered English Writing Tool: A Hermeneutic Phenomenological Approach

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Abstract

This study aimed to describe and interpret campus writers' experiences in using Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool. Campus writers used Grammarly to improve their writing performance, which included their grammatical accuracy and proper use of mechanics. The researcher used a phenomenological qualitative method by Moustakas (1994) to explore the phenomenon of the use of Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool by campus writers. The student participants of the study were five (5) SHS campus English writers. Purposive sampling was applied since the needed participants were students with distinct writing experiences in and out of the school. The researcher purposely chose students who were considered campus writers and users of Grammarly. The study revealed that Grammarly improved campus writers' writing performance as it helped them ensure grammatical accuracy and proper use of mechanics in their writing. However, comprehensively reviewing the suggestions provided by Grammarly was necessary to avoid misleading feedback that caused deviation from the original meaning of the text. Meanwhile, campus writers mentioned some considerations before accepting the suggestions.

Keywords: *campus writers, writing experiences, Grammarly, and AI-powered English writing tool*

Introduction

Writing is a fundamental skill in language learning (Tusyanah et al., 2019). It plays a vital role in students' learning since it is needed to support the learners' academic success (Aliyu, 2020). The ability to know, comprehend, and articulate a concept into a paragraph or essay is the most basic writing skill that students can possess (Yamin, 2019). It requires them to employ their knowledge of the language, such as grammar, punctuation, spelling, and vocabulary, and make good connections among sentences. It also involves using appropriate language, tone, and style to communicate the intended message while taking into account the audience and purpose of the written communication. Khazrouni (2019) also claimed that English writing skills play an essential role in developing several skills in English learning, such as analyzing, arguing, and critical thinking. However, despite its significance, many students encounter challenges when acquiring proficiency in writing. Most learners do not quite have the organization of thoughts, mastery of needed vocabulary is still less, and they still lack ideas in construction as well as grammar use (Akbar & Picard, 2019; Patak et al., 2021; Pongsapan & Patak, 2021). Moreover, writing requires organizing thoughts logically and coherently, conveying them in various written languages, and adhering to different writing rules (Fitria, 2021). This is also where writing becomes difficult.

Basically, writing is a skill that the students must master as it helps them achieve communicative competence. For campus writers who are exposed to several writing activities in and out of the school, communicative competence is a key component of their writing journey. Though they are already good at writing, they also experience difficulties in writing texts with proper grammar or applying writing rules according to writing standards. Because of this, writers often seek digital tools popularly known as Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools that can improve their writing, ensuring it is clear, concise, and error-free. Adopting AI-powered writing tools can help students improve their writing (Kurniati & Fithriani, 2022; Wang, 2022; Zhao, 2022). There are many AI or digital tools available on the internet, such as Google Docs, Wordtune, QuillBot, and Grammarly. These tools have been found to improve students' writing skills significantly. They use advanced algorithms to identify common errors in grammar, punctuation, and syntax and provide suggestions to improve clarity and style. They also help paraphrase and refine sentences for enhanced effectiveness.

Grammarly is the AI-powered English writing tool used by campus writers. It is the most widely and commonly used English grammar checker development tool (Fitria, 2021). It is an Artificial Intelligence (AI) tool that is used as a writing aid to help writers check for various types of language errors or grammar errors in English. It checks grammar and spelling, detects plagiarism, and offers advice on writing clarity, concision, vocabulary, style, and tone. On the other hand, although AI tools like Grammarly can be helpful, they cannot replace human creativity and originality in terms of creative expression through language. While Grammarly is an able resource for perfecting written work, it should not be considered a substitute for human intelligence. With these being said, understanding how student writers or campus writers use Grammarly as an English writing tool is essential for ensuring the quality of writing.

According to Dizon and Gayed (2021), on Examining the impact of Grammarly on the quality of mobile L2 Writing, Grammarly had a significant, positive effect on grammatical accuracy and lexical richness but not really on writing fluency and syntactic complexity on L2 students compared to a control condition which did not allow for the use of any writing aids, digital or otherwise. However, since only four aspects of L2 writing were focused in the study and students' perceptions were not explored, it is difficult to make broad generalizations from the findings. The study of Kesi Fitriana and Laeli Nurazni (2022) on Exploring English Department Students' Perceptions on Using Grammarly to Check the Grammar in Their Writing showed that Grammarly has both advantages and drawbacks:

Grammarly helps students check their grammar in writing and helps them learn by themselves. However, corrections from Grammarly sometimes change the meaning of sentences (Kesi Fitriana & Laeli Nurazni, 2022). The researchers believed that their study had its drawbacks and recommended conducting further research on the same topic but for different participants, such as senior high school students, to better understand views towards this tool in aiding students' writing.

From the results of the study of Dizon and Gayed (2021) and Kesi Fitriana and Laeli Nurazni (2022), the researcher perceived that there was a need to conduct a study on the experiences of students in using Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool to better understand their views on the use of Grammarly. The researcher chose the SHS campus English writers as participants to have a different group of participants. Moreover, since there was a problem encountered with the suggestions or corrections provided by Grammarly, this study also explored how campus writers interpreted or evaluated the suggestions provided by Grammarly. This was to have the idea that the suggestions or corrections provided by Grammarly should be reviewed or proofread before accepting them. The future findings of this study were intended to help remedy the problems mentioned

Research Questions

This hermeneutic phenomenological study aimed to describe and interpret the use of Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool for SHS campus writers in the two (2) selected public schools in Quezon City. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of the campus writers in using Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool?
2. How do campus writers describe their experiences in using Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool?
3. How do campus writers evaluate and interpret the suggested Input or feedback provided by Grammarly?

Literature Review

According to Tussyah, Anissa, Chayatina, Sakitri, and Utami (2019), writing is a fundamental skill in language learning. It is essential for academic success, professional advancement, and effective communication in the digital age. Specifically, it has a vital role for learners to develop several skills in their English learning (Khazrouni, 2019). Besides, learners are encouraged to make use of their understanding of micro linguistics, such as morphology, syntax, and semantics, that have already been learned in class (Menggo et al., 2019). However, though writing is essential, it is also considered one of the most challenging skills to learn. It is supported by the statements that writing is such a difficult task involving many cognitive and language skills. Nation (2020) argues that writing involves complex thinking skills and unique ways of organizing and presenting the writing that deserves attention. It requires organizing thoughts logically and coherently, conveying them in various written languages, and adhering to different writing rules (Fitria, 2021). Moreover, developing one's writing skills requires proficiency in grammar, especially in English (Fitria et al., 2022). This is another reason why writing has become difficult.

Lim and Phua (2019) state that students' writing skills can be enhanced using digital tools. Due to technological advancements, students can use various programs/tools like Artificial Intelligence to help them write independently. Nazari et al. (2021) define AI as the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, especially computer systems. AI writing tools analyze written materials and provide feedback on writing, such as grammar, vocabulary, syntax, content, and structure (Hosseini et al., 2023; Strobl et al., 2019; Thorp, 2023). They are easy to use and effective and help students and educators save time and effort (T. S. Chang et al., 2021; Gayed et al., 2022; Jeanjaroonsri, 2023; Zhao, 2022). Bouchoux (2019) states that there are some easy and free AI tools that students can use to improve their writing. Some of them are QuillBot, Wordtune, and Grammarly. These tools have been found to improve students' writing skills significantly.

Utilizing AI-powered writing tools can help students improve their writing (e.g., Kurniati & Fithriani, 2022; Wang, 2022; Zhao, 2022); however, there are still concerns about the side effect of these tools (e.g., Y. Liu et al., 2022; Lund & Wang, 2023; Qadir, 2022). For instance, AI writing tools may inadvertently promote over-reliance among students, as they might rely too much on these tools for correction without thoroughly understanding their mistakes.

On the other hand, Grammarly is known to be the most widely and commonly used English grammar checker development tool (Fitria, 2021). It is designed to assist individuals in writing texts to minimize the mistakes caused by human oversight (Arisandi & Sudarajat, 2023). This digital writing tool checks grammar and spelling, detects plagiarism, and offers advice on writing clarity, concision, vocabulary, style, and tone (Grammarly, 2023). With recommendations from Grammarly, the user's vocabulary will grow because of this application's input on proper spelling, which improves the sentence's context and corrects word usage errors.

In a study by O'Neill and Russell (2019), it was found that Grammarly is an effective tool as it may help provide input to students to improve their grammatical accuracy, encouraging self-confidence and autonomy in the editing stages of writing. Aside from grammar, Grammarly improves stylistic expression and locates lexical errors while also offering alternative phrasing for written sentences (Barrot, 2020). Gain et al. (2019) also noted that the usage of Grammarly's virtual application could help with spelling checker tools at the work of academics and sciences. This application also functions very well in improving writing styles, such as writing or guiding students to write concise language briefly in paragraphs with precise and concise sentences. This tool is shown to be more effective in

reducing errors in terms of vocabulary usage (diction), language use (grammar), and mechanics of writing (spelling and punctuation). Of those many advantages, it could be reflected that Grammarly is a practical application for students writing.

Apart from the positive results and advantages of Grammarly, several criticisms have still been raised regarding its effectiveness (Pratama, 2020). A study by O'Neill and Russell (2019) stated that both students and the academic learning advisors (ALAs) had issues with Grammarly missing errors, misrepresenting errors, giving inaccurate advice, and generating too much feedback, which harmed students' confidence. Though Grammarly improved their effectiveness and efficiency when reviewing students' work, they noted that Grammarly's suggestions were occasionally inaccurate and that excessive feedback was generated. Sometimes, grammar corrections are incorrect, and program revisions can change the meaning of sentences (Fitria, 2022). Although it offers detailed feedback on language proficiency, there are still specific faults that the program cannot catch and some misleading feedback (Wardatin et al., 2022). Thus, it is still important to review or proofread the suggestions or feedback provided by Grammarly to check if they fit the context of your writing. Also, it is to check the readability of your written work and if it is clear and comprehensible on the part of the readers.

Most research only focuses on students' general perceptions of using Grammarly applications in writing. Others have only considered limited aspects/features of Grammarly. Moreover, little attention has been paid to students who are exposed to more challenging writing tasks, like the campus writers who are also users of Grammarly. Therefore, the present study aims to determine and describe campus writers' experiences in using Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool and to find out how they interpret or evaluate the suggestions provided by Grammarly. Campus writers' experiences would then be interpreted to determine perceptions. Yusup and Suryaman (2021) explain that students' perceptions can influence whether or not the learning process is successful. Thus, studies must consider students' perceptions when determining if Grammarly aids students or causes them to experience difficulties or misunderstandings.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a qualitative research design, specifically hermeneutic phenomenological design by Max van Manen (1990), to describe and interpret the lived experiences of the campus writers in using Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool and find out how they interpreted or evaluated the suggestions provided by Grammarly. This was so because a qualitative design describes the meaning of several individuals' lived experiences of a concept or a phenomenon (Creswell, 2007). Also, a hermeneutic phenomenological design explores and interprets the lived experiences of individuals within a specific context, with a focus on uncovering the deeper meanings and essences inherent in human existence (Manen, 1990). It also seeks reality from individuals' narratives of their experiences and feelings and produces in-depth descriptions and interpretations of the concept or phenomenon.

The study involved an in-depth interview to collect data from the participants to elicit rich, detailed narratives about their experiences with Grammarly. It consisted of open-ended questions to encourage participants to reflect on their experiences, perceptions, and interpretations related to using Grammarly. Arts-based data were also used to explore and understand more of the data given by the campus writers, as well as observations or feedback from the paper advisers to support the data given by the participants. The three (3) data collection methods helped the researcher explore and interpret the experiences of campus writers using Grammarly, uncovering the meanings and insights inherent in their interactions with the tool.

On the other hand, ontology was considered its philosophical underpinning. Ontology is the philosophical study of the nature of reality. In terms of education, it is the philosophical study of the nature of educational reality and how there may be different perceptions of what is known.

Participants

The participants were the five (5) campus writers whom the paper advisers of the two (2) selected public schools in Quezon City recommended.

A purposive sampling technique was used for student participants. It is when the researcher relied on her judgment when choosing members of the population to participate according to the study's purpose. In this study, the researcher used a purposive sampling technique since the needed participants were students with distinct writing experiences in and out of the school. The researcher purposely chose students who were considered campus writers and users of Grammarly. The paper adviser of the first selected public school recommended one (1) of her writers who met the criteria. The paper adviser of the other public school also recommended four (4) of her writers who also met the criteria.

The following criteria were taken into consideration when choosing the participants:

- The participant must be a Senior High School (SHS) student.
- The participant must be an English campus writer.
- The participant must be a user of Grammarly for six months or more.
- The participant must be using Grammarly not only in their academic writing but also in their journalistic writing.
- The participant must be willing to participate in the study.

Instruments

This study utilized an in-depth interview to determine and describe campus writers' experiences in using Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool and to find out how they evaluated or interpreted the suggestions provided by Grammarly. The researcher also utilized arts-based data to explore and understand the data given by the campus writers. Moreover, observations or feedback from the paper advisers were also requested to support the data given by the participants. The questions that were used in the in-depth interview were drafted by the researcher.

The in-depth phenomenological interview was the primary instrument that the researcher used in collecting data. The researcher conducted one-on-one interviews with the campus writers who have been using Grammarly for six months or more. The interview was conducted face-to-face and online. The researcher used an interview guide that included open-ended questions to allow the campus writers to share their experiences, insights, and reflections. It contained questions that were based on the Statement of the Problem (SOP). It consisted of three parts. The first part determined the experiences of the campus writers in using Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool. The second described the experiences of the campus writers in using Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool. The third part was to find out how campus writers evaluated or interpreted the suggestions or feedback provided by Grammarly.

The questions that were used in the in-depth interview were checked by the researcher's adviser after going through content validation. To ensure a valid and reliable research instrument, the researcher sought help from professional experts for recommendations, suggestions, and some input. The purpose was to improve the first draft concerning grammar and sentence construction, ambiguities, duplications, and relativity. Their comments and suggestions were considered for the improvement and refinement of the questions used. Also, the researcher conducted a try-out or pilot testing for students who were also writers and users of Grammarly but not participants in the study.

After the interview with the campus writers, the researcher asked them to provide samples of their written outputs before and after using Grammarly (for arts-based data) according to their roles and functions in journalism. This was to see how they used Grammarly and how it improved their writing. Then, she requested the paper advisers via Messenger to give their observations or feedback on the campus writers' writing performance to confirm the data given by them. Documentation for the one-on-one interview, arts-based data, and observations or feedback was done to support this study.

Procedure

Before conducting an in-depth interview, the researcher prepared a letter of request to be signed by the research adviser and coordinator of the Master of Arts in Education addressed to the School's Division Superintendent (SDS) of Quezon City seeking permission to conduct the study in the two (2) selected public schools. Before the researcher submitted the letter to the Division Office for the record section to receive, she first sought help from professional experts in checking and validating the interview guide since it needed to be attached to the letter. After that, the researcher went to the division office to submit the letter to the record section. The researcher was informed that she needed to wait for 1-2 weeks for the letter to be approved. Due to time constraints, she requested to proceed to the interview even without the approved letter yet, and she only had the received copy of the letter.

The researcher sent a letter to the participants as well as the informed consent form that they needed to sign before participating in the study. The signed consent forms from the parents/guardians of the participants whose age was below 17 were also required. The availability of the participants was also considered. Moreover, they were given a thorough explanation of the purpose and nature of the study. The interviews were done face-to-face and online based on the preferences of the participants. The interview process was explained to them first. All the responses were audio recorded and documented with the permission of the participants. The audio recording was used in transcribing the participants' responses. After each interview with the campus writers, the researcher requested a sample of their written works before and after using Grammarly. Sample outputs were sent via Messenger in an image file to see the highlighted errors as well as the suggestions of Grammarly, as well as the edited version of their written outputs. After all the interviews, the researcher contacted the paper advisers to request their observations or feedback on the campus writers' writing performance. The observations or feedback were also sent via Messenger. With the provided sample outputs and observations or feedback, the researcher checked if they confirmed or supported the campus writers' interview responses.

Facing a few challenges and problems in the data gathering was inevitable. The researcher had a problem with the participants since she did not make sure beforehand that the campus writers whom she chose were all English writers. The researcher just found out that most of her chosen participants were Filipino writers and that only one (1) among the ten (10) chosen participants was an English writer. Thus, she was pressured and stressed to find another set of participants. She spent time and effort to find the participants. In connection to this, since the researcher found other participants in another school, she had to go back to the division office to send another letter since she had to include the name of the other school in it. After a week, she went back to the division office to claim the letter. However, the letter that they gave her was the approved letter of her first request, which did not include the other school. She was told that they did not notice the change in the letter. Because of that, she had to wait for another week. After receiving the approved copy of the letter, the researcher went to the office of the principal of the said schools to have them receive the letter. Since the principals were not there at that time, the officers in charge noted and received the letter.

The time frame for data gathering was done in almost a month. After that, the researcher compiled and consolidated all the responses

(audio-recording), including the sample written outputs before and after using Grammarly, as well as the observations or feedback from the paper advisers. Then, the researcher analyzed, transcribed, described, and interpreted the results to discuss the outcome of the study. For the transcription, it took two weeks for the researcher to transcribe all the answers of the participants due to the difficulties she experienced. The gathered data was arranged into tabular format following the participants' responses, codes, categories, themes, and life world elements. Afterward, the researcher drew conclusions and recommendations for the completion of the study. The five (5) participants were identified using a pseudonym or pen name in all data collection, analysis, and results to protect their privacy.

Ethical Considerations

Adherence to ethical principles such as informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation enhances the reliability and validity of research outcomes (Jones, 2019). In conducting the study, the researcher took into account the ethical considerations that should be followed. The researcher first submitted a letter of request, addressed to the School Division Superintendent, to the Division Office of Quezon City. After the letter had been approved, it was submitted to the principal or officers in charge of the two (2) respective schools, though there was a delay in the letter, as mentioned in the data gathering procedure.

The participants, on the other hand, were given complete information about what it means for them to take part, and they gave their consent before they entered the research. They were treated with the utmost respect and were given the right to privacy and confidentiality of their given information by anonymizing their personal information and ensuring secure storage of data. Pseudonyms were used to protect participants' identities in research reports. The researcher also assured the participants that they would not be disturbed by the performance of their regular classes and duties while collecting data.

Before conducting the study, the researcher made sure that the participants had a better understanding of the research and its purpose. Methods and procedures that were used were disclosed to the participants. Moreover, only the researcher and the research adviser, together with the referred experts, were knowledgeable about the flow and progress of the study.

Results and Discussion

After the data were analyzed, six (6) themes and eleven (11) categories were generated.

Experiences of the campus writers in using Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool

Theme 1: Improving writing performance while learning

The use of Grammarly helped improve participants' writing performances, including grammatical accuracy and proper use of mechanics. They also learned from the corrections made by Grammarly.

Category 1: Fewer mistakes and easier writing experience

Grammarly helped campus writers with their grammar and text structure. It analyzed their sentences and corrected any mistakes they made. Also, it was of great help in expanding their vocabulary. This tool provided them with an easier writing experience.

The three (3) participants had the same experiences when using Grammarly. Based on the responses, Grammarly helped them check their grammar and structure.

Participant 1 mentioned "*ginagamit ko po sya para po maayos po yung structures... structures ng sentences ko...*" (L62-63).

This was also shown in his sample output and in the observations or feedback from his paper adviser, where he had a problem with technicalities or the grammar aspects or structures, but Grammarly provided suggestions that helped him correct his grammatical errors and fixed his sentence structure.

Participant 2 "*checking my grammar... I use Grammarly to confirm or correct any mistakes that I make when writing my article*" (L37-40).

This was also shown in his sample output and in the observations or feedback from his paper adviser, where he had grammar and spelling issues, but Grammarly provided suggestions that helped him correct his grammatical and spelling errors improving his grammatical accuracy.

Participant 4 "*I'm also using it for grammar coherency... sa pagkakaalam ko lang if may idouble tap po yung word lalabas po yung mga synonyms, yung mga words na yun to avoid redundancy...*" (L87-91).

This was also shown in her sample output and in the observations or feedback from her paper adviser where she had a problem with grammar coherency including the use of prepositions and transitional devices but Grammarly provided suggestions that helped her improve her grammatical coherency.

On the other hand, two (2) participants had the same experiences in Grammarly providing an easier writing experience.

Participant 2 mentioned "*It's very efficient for me because it saved a lot of time*" (L36-38). *It's easier when I have Grammarly because ahm it makes things easier and faster because of how useful it is when it comes to correcting my mistakes* (L177-180).

Participant 5 said “*mas mapapadali po yung... yung work po natin as a campus journalist*” (L47-50).

The responses of Participants 2 and 5 were also reflected in their sample outputs and in the observations or feedback from their paper adviser, where the edited version of their outputs with the aid of Grammarly was more polished and improved.

The results validated the statement of Vitalis et al. (2021) that Grammarly was shown to be more effective in reducing errors in terms of vocabulary usage (diction), language use (grammar), and mechanics of writing (spelling and punctuation). It is designed to assist individuals in writing texts to minimize the mistakes caused by human oversight (Arisandi & Sudarajat, 2023). Moreover, Grammarly evaluated writing very quickly (Fahmi & Cahyono, 2021), and with the recommendation of correction from Grammarly, the users would know how to revise their writing. Besides, Grammarly is easy, and it only takes them a short time to use (Pratama, 2020).

With these being said, it can be interpreted that Grammarly helped campus writers minimize their grammar mistakes in writing because of its grammar checker feature. It helped them correct the mistakes they made. It can also be said that Grammarly made their writing easier since it evaluated their writing very quickly, and they saved much time as it helped them finish their writing faster. Moreover, since real-time feedback is provided as one type, highlighting errors and suggesting corrections instantly, this allowed them to address mistakes as they occur, rather than having to go back and edit after, streamlining the writing process. It also allowed them to save time.

Category 2: Gained learnings

Feedback from Grammarly not only helped campus writers polish their work but also helped them learn from it.

The four (4) participants had the same experiences in Grammarly in improving their writing performances.

Participant 1 mentioned “*Naiimprove naman po nya in a way that ah chinecheck nya po yung mismong grammar ko and kinocorrect nya po yung mga ahm mga maling ah grammar grammatical errors po... (L74-76) Gamit po yung mga corrections nya natututo rin po ako kung paano magsulat nang maayos and paano po magconstruct ng sentences nang maayos po (L77-79).*”

Participant 2 “*Yes, ma’am. It improves my writing performance (L42). When I write, it corrects my mistakes which I also learned by observing the mistakes I make because it doesn’t just correct my mistake, it also shows me what mistakes I did (L44-46)*”

Participant 4 “*Yes po kasi po from yung kung ikocompare ko yung gawa ko noon at sa gawa ko ngayon, big difference po talaga sya and hindi na po masyadong redundant yung ibang words ko po, so masasabi ko naman po na nag improve yung gawa ko from last time while using Grammarly po (L121-124).*”

Participant 5 “*Yes naman po ma’am (L68). Yung writing skills ko po is medyo flowery, with the help of Grammarly po mas pinasimple nya po yung words since ang kailangan po sa news article is conciseness po... (L70-73).*”

The responses of Participants 1, 2, 4, and 5 were also reflected in their sample outputs and in the observations or feedback from their paper advisers, where their writing performances had improved with the aid of Grammarly.

The participants’ statements aligned with the study of O’Neill and Russell (2019). It was stated that Grammarly is an effective tool as it may help provide input to students to improve their grammatical accuracy, encouraging self-confidence and autonomy in the editing stages of writing.

With these being said, it can be interpreted that when using Grammarly, campus writers did not just get a chance to correct their mistakes but also learned from those mistakes. As Grammarly corrected mistakes, it also explained why certain corrections were necessary, helping campus writers understand grammar principles better. Thus, they gained valuable learnings that they used even offline, allowing them to write independently.

Theme 2: Deviating from the original meaning

Grammarly sometimes provided suggestions that changed the meaning of the text. Thus, comprehensively reviewing the suggestions was necessary.

Category: Providing irrelevant/inappropriate suggestions

Apart from the positive results and advantages of the use of Grammarly, there were also issues that campus writers encountered like giving inaccurate or irrelevant suggestions that changed the intended meaning of the text.

The three (3) participants had the same experiences when Grammarly sometimes provided irrelevant and inappropriate suggestions.

Participant 1 said “*...nagsasuggest po sya ng ibang sentence na ayun nga po naiiba po yung ibig sabihin nung sentence mo na yun and kapag ganun naman po dinidiregard ko nalang po yung ano.. (L93-95).*”

Participant 4 said “*Nag o-auto po sya kapag may ginamit ka po na word na hindi English but need to be part in the ano po yung sinusulat nyo po, kunyari ah tagalog po sya tapos bigla pong aano magiging.. maiiba po yung word kasi hindi pa po recognize ni Grammarly yung word na yun... (L139-142) “...sometimes po kasi yung mga sinasuggest pong word ni Grammarly is hindi naman po sya angkop talaga po dun sa sinusulat nyo po (L161-163).*”

Participant 5 said *“Ma’am since Grammarly is AI po and more prone po yung AI sa accidents and mistakes, I think relying on... relying on Grammarly too much po is can... or can alter yung pagiging... or can alter po yung way nung pagsusulat po ng news article and minsan po since AI nga po sya na and common or prone sya sa mga mistakes, minsan po hindi po concise or relevant po yung mga suggestions po na ibinigay sa inyo (L80-85).*

The responses of Participants 1, 4, and 5 were also shown in their sample outputs, where they dismissed or ignored some of the suggestions from Grammarly since they were not relevant to the intended meaning of their texts.

The results confirmed Fitria's (2022) findings that sometimes, grammar corrections from Grammarly are incorrect, and program revisions can change the meaning of sentences. This is the same with Kesi Fitriana and Laeli Nurazni's (2022) findings that corrections from Grammarly sometimes change the meaning of sentences. This tool might not also be able to fully grasp the subtleties and nuances of human language and emotion, which can lead to suggestions that may not be appropriate or accurate in a given context (Haleem et al., 2022).

Based on participants' responses and related literature, it is explained that campus writers also encountered problems when using Grammarly. While Grammarly strived to provide helpful suggestions for improving writing, there were instances where it offered irrelevant or inappropriate suggestions that caused a change in the meaning of the sentence or text, different from what campus writers really wanted to convey. Also, since Grammarly was used to make the text more concise, it usually removed words that were actually necessary to the text. It also changed the words that it did not recognize, like Filipino words.

Theme 3: Grammarly over other AI tools

Grammarly was chosen by the participants due to the comfort it gave to long-time users, the positive feedback given by its users, and the influence of friends and social media.

Category 1: Long-time user's comfortability

Long-time users of Grammarly had developed a strong sense of comfort and familiarity with the tool. Over time, they became accustomed to its features and the way it assisted them in their writing process.

The four (4) participants had the same experience in using Grammarly for a long time.

Participant 2 mentioned *“I'm more comfortable using Grammarly because I know how to use it and I mean, I know the entire mechanic of Grammarly... (L206-208)”*

Participant 3 *“Very easy to use po yung Grammarly (L135). Matagal na po kasi ako sa Grammarly, and ayun po (L142).”*

Participant 4 *“Si Grammarly, for grammar lang po talaga sya parang dun na po ako mag istick as of now since matagal ko narin naman syang ginagamit and has been proven naman po based sa experiences ko na okay si Grammarly and nakakahelp sa productivity si Grammarly po (L214-217).”*

Participant 5 *“Actually mas gamay po ako sa Grammarly po since ayun po yung efficient and accessible way po (L114-115).”*

The responses of Participants 2, 3, 4, and 5 were also reflected in their sample outputs and in the observations or feedback from their paper adviser, where they showed that they had already been using Grammarly since then.

The results were somewhat aligned with Fitriana & Nurazni's (2022) study, which stated that Grammarly is renowned for being user-friendly. Based on several comprehensive reviews, students using Grammarly report increased writing confidence (Setyani et al., 2023) since they become more proficient in writing. With them knowing that Grammarly is widely recognized as the most accurate and extensively utilized English grammar checker globally (O'Neill & Russell, 2019).

With these being mentioned, the campus writers chose to use Grammarly since they started using it for a long time; they had become used to it and comfortable with it. With their experiences, Grammarly has been proven to be helpful to their writing. As long-time users of Grammarly, they have already developed a high level of comfort and familiarity with the tool, which has contributed to a smoother and more efficient writing experience.

Category 2: Peer/Media influence

Peer and media influence can play significant roles in shaping campus writers' decisions to use Grammarly.

The three (3) participants shared the same experiences when it comes to how they learned about Grammarly.

Participant 1 mentioned *“Influence rin po siguro nung mas maraming users ang gumagamit preferred na gumagamit ng Grammarly based on the reviews... (L129-130).”*

Participant 2 *“It's faster po ma'am and most of my friends at school also use Grammarly and they've been having a lot of positive opinions about it. So, I use it (L103-105).”*

Participant 4 *“So nakilala ko po si Grammarly dahil sa isang advertisement nila sa YouTube (L203-204). ...nung nagamay gamay ko na po si Grammarly onti and I learned to love Grammarly na po since ayun nga po yung benefits po ni Grammarly is napakarame kahit na you’re just using Free version po (L207-209).”*

The results confirmed that Grammarly is known to be the most widely and commonly used English grammar checker development tool (Fitria, 2021).

Considering the participants' responses, it can be interpreted that positive feedback from friends or peers influenced them to try Grammarly. Hearing about others' positive experiences with the tool prompted them to explore it themselves. Furthermore, engaging advertisements that highlight Grammarly's features and benefits captured their attention and motivated them to explore the tool further. Upon experiencing its benefits, the participants were urged to continue to use the tool.

Descriptions of campus writers' experiences in using Grammarly as an AI-powered English writing tool

Theme 4: A great tool for refining text

Grammarly is considered a reliable and useful tool for refining participants' written works, as it helps them correct their mistakes in grammar and mechanics.

Category 1: Reliability of the tool

Grammarly is considered a reliable tool for grammar. It often provides feedback or suggestions that improve grammatical accuracy.

The four (4) participants had the same descriptions of their experiences with Grammarly.

Participant 1 mentioned *“Grammarly is reliable, Grammarly is easy to use, Grammarly is ahm easy to access ... (L164).”*

Participant 2 *“For me Grammarly is reliable (L183).”*

Participant 4 *“Okay po si Grammarly pagdating sa mga grammar. ...ayun nga po maganda po syang gamitin... (L241-243) It’s a great tool it’s a great help for students lalo na po.. lalo na po if wala ka naman pong masyadong alam nga po sa grammar... (L261-263).”*

Participant 5 *“Reliable po sya as a.. as a tool for our.. for writing articles and papers po... (L329-330).”*

The responses of Participants 1, 2, 4, and 5 were also reflected in their sample outputs and in the observations or feedback from their paper advisers, where the use of Grammarly helped them refine their texts and improve their writing.

The statements confirmed Vitalis et al. (2021) research findings that participants were quite satisfied with the effectiveness of the Grammarly application for correcting their writing's grammar.

With these being said, it can be interpreted that Grammarly was indeed a reliable tool for refining texts. It analyzed the text structure and fixed grammatical issues. It provided suggestions that made participants' writing better, though it was also mentioned that double-checking the suggestions should be done to ensure they are appropriate to the writing context.

Category 2: Usefulness of the tool

Grammarly is a valuable and useful tool for writers, assisting with grammar and mechanics and ultimately helping them produce articles.

The five (5) participants had the same statements on how useful Grammarly is.

Participant 1 said *“Inaayos nya po yung structure (L233)” Grammarly helps me to ah itama yung maling ano maling uses ng technical ano ng pagsusulat po kaya ayun po (L236-237).”*

Participant 2 said *“I describe it as it’s pretty good... (L110) To me, Grammarly has been pretty useful (L115)” ...it helps me refine my written work (L169). It helps me ah clean up messes I make when writing like as I’ve said, the grammar (L171-172)”*

Participant 3 said *“Yun nga po, napakauseful nya and napakadaling gamitin (L216). Hmm..10 out of 10 po (L219).”*

Participant 4 said *“...naenhance nya pa po lalo yung writings ko and articles (L337-338).”*

Participant 5 said *“When it comes to ah grammar context, to punctualization, capitalization ah summarizing and paraphrasing, it’s ah very good naman po since it is very useful nga po... (L200-202).”*

The responses of Participants 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 were also reflected in their sample outputs and in the observations or feedback from their paper advisers, where they showed how useful Grammarly was in improving their writing, especially to grammatical accuracy and proper use of mechanics.

The results validated Aidil's (2021) investigation of students' perception of the "Grammarly application" students' effectiveness; it was concurred that Grammarly was valuable for learning scholastic composition. The information showed that this program had given free

openness, programmed amendment, and helpful or useful input. Grammarly also has benefits in improving grammar in students' writing (Fitriana & Nurazni, 2022).

With these being said, it can be interpreted that Grammarly is indeed useful for refining text. It is useful in fixing technical issues like grammar, mechanics, and even text structure. It also enhances writing skills that surely contribute to better and more refined writing texts.

For the first two research questions, the phenomenon was anchored on the theoretical framework of the Input Hypothesis of Stephen Krashen (1980). From the current knowledge of the campus writers (i), Grammarly provided suggestions or input (+1) for them to consider for the improvement of their writing. Grammarly helped them correct their grammar mistakes to produce better outputs. However, they still comprehended the input to know its relevance to their texts since suggestions or corrections from Grammarly sometimes changed the meaning of sentences. It was similar to the findings of Kesi Fitriana and Laeli Nurazni (2022) that Grammarly helped students check their grammar in writing and helped them learn by themselves. However, corrections from Grammarly sometimes changed the meaning of sentences.

It was evident from the aforementioned theoretical framework that Grammarly enhanced the student's quality of writing by checking the grammar and structure of their text. However, comprehending the input or suggestions provided by Grammarly was necessary before considering them in the text.

How campus writers evaluate or interpret the suggested input or feedback Grammarly provides

Theme 5: Reviewing the provided suggestions/feedback

Before accepting the suggestions provided by Grammarly, comprehensively reviewing their relevance and accuracy to the writing context is necessary.

Category 1: Relevance of the suggestions

Suggestions from Grammarly need to be reviewed first based on their relevance to the text before being used.

The three (3) participants had the same statements that before accepting the suggestions provided by Grammarly, it was necessary to check and consider their relevance to the text.

Participant 3 mentioned said *"Iniisip ko po muna kung aakma po talaga sa sinusulat ko (L284). Pero yung kapag mali po talaga, ayun po binabago ko po (L308-309)" Yung relativity po nung ano.. ng suggestion, kung related po ba sya.. or..ay kung yung gusto ko po bang sabihin ay naibibigay nya (L329-330)"*

Participant 4 said *"...if yung pinapalit po nila or tinatangal nilang words is still connected po sa mga ginagawa ko...(L424-425)."*

Participant 5 said *"Sometimes po ma'am. Ayun nga po since ano po sila sa mistakes, minsan hindi po talaga tumutugma nga po yung mga suggestions po nila dun po sa gusto kong maparating (L386-388).*

The responses of Participants 3, 4, and 5 were also reflected in their sample outputs, where it was shown that there were some suggestions that they did not accept due to irrelevance.

The results confirmed that although Grammarly offers detailed feedback on language proficiency, there are still specific faults that the program cannot catch and some misleading feedback (Wardatin et al., 2022). Hidayatun et al. (2021) stated that students need to take advantage of using Grammarly in the proper context so they can be aware of their own mistakes. Students need to develop their awareness and understanding of English grammar rules.

Based on their responses, it can be interpreted that reviewing the suggestions provided by Grammarly is essential to ensure that they enhance rather than detract from your writing. It is necessary to consider the relevance of the suggestions to the text. Sometimes, Grammarly provides suggestions that are irrelevant to the text, like trying to change a part of the text that is not supposed to be changed, which can lead to a deviation in meaning from the original one.

Category 2: Accuracy of the suggestions

Grammarly's suggestions are generally accurate; however, they are not infallible. It sometimes provides inaccurate suggestions. Thus, reviewing them critically is necessary to determine which suggestions to accept or ignore.

The five (5) participants had the same idea of considering the accuracy of the suggestions provided by Grammarly before accepting them.

Participant 1 said *"Not all the time. May mga time lang po na.. siguro po sa mga name ng.. siguro po sa mga names ng cities iko-correct nya ganun kahit naman po hindi ganun (L314-315). Sometimes accurate, sometimes hindi (L320)."*

Participant 2 said, *"Sometimes it's accurate but sometimes it's not" (L262-263).* Participant 3 said *"Yun nga po sinabi ko po minsan (L343)."*

Participant 4 said “...*dun po talaga sa pagtatanggal ng ibang words ako hindi masyadong ano kay Grammarly since parang nawawala po yung fluency siguro pag kapag descriptive po ganun (L406-408).*”

Participant 5 said “*If appropriate po sya for the readers or for the audiences, I think mas better ko po na gagamitin ko po yun... (L336-337)*” “*...kung hindi po sya correct pakinggan or parang nagdadoubt ka po kung tama po yung grammatical coherency mo po ah I think hindi po.. hindi ko po itutuloy...(L357-359).*”

The responses of Participants 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 were also reflected in their sample outputs, where the accuracy of the suggestions provided by Grammarly was checked first before accepting them.

The results are somehow aligned with Wardatin et al. (2022), stating that Grammarly sometimes provides misleading feedback.

Based on participants’ answers, it can be said that other than relevance, it is also important to check the accuracy of the suggestions provided by Grammarly. The participants had some experiences that the suggestions they got from Grammarly were sometimes inaccurate and inappropriate, such as when omitting or changing words or sentences that were not supposed to be omitted or changed or suggesting something that was not meant to be included in the text.

Theme 6: Considering the writing context

Writing context should be considered before accepting Grammarly suggestions, ensuring that the writing structure is intact and the text is readable or comprehensible.

Category 1: Keeping the structure intact

Grammarly analyzed the context of a sentence to provide more relevant suggestions. However, there may be instances where it led to suggestions that were not entirely accurate.

The two (2) participants answered about considering the context of their writing when deciding to accept the suggestions provided by Grammarly.

Participant 2 said “*...when Grammarly suggests me I think about whether I should replace it and if I don’t need to, I just let it change but still keeps the old structure intact (L215-217)*” *...that it wouldn’t change too much of what I did already. I just want things to be clean. I don’t.. I mean, I just want my text to be clean. I don’t want it to change in any other way (L258-260).*”

Participant 4 “*First of all po is yung context ng sinusulat ko...(L423).*”

The responses of Participants 2 and 4 were also reflected in their sample outputs, where it was shown that the context of the edited version of their articles was still the same and intact, though corrections were applied.

The statements confirmed Hidayatun et al. (2021), stating that students need to take advantage of using Grammarly in the proper context so they can be aware of their own mistakes.

With these being said, it can be interpreted that the writing context should be considered before accepting the suggestions provided by Grammarly. Since it sometimes provides irrelevant or inaccurate suggestions, one should know their context so they would be able to decode the suggestions provided if it is aligned with their writing context.

Category 2: Readability of the text

Grammarly provides valuable suggestions to enhance text readability which is essential in helping writers craft text that is clear, concise, and engaging.

The two (2) participants said that readability is one of the things that should be considered before accepting the suggestions provided by Grammarly.

Participant 4 said “*Sakin po si Grammarly first naimprove nya po yung writing skills ko since sa mga suggestions and whatsoever po nya na features tapos na naenhance nya din po yung readability ng sulat ko po (L439-441).*”

Participant 5 said “*I based on the audiences din po and sometimes to myself kung naintindihan ba tong synonym na to or kung alam ba kaya nila ito.. kung alam nila then gagamitin ko, kung hindi naman nila alam then mag istick po ako sa common terminology po (L349-352).*”

The responses of Participants 4 and 5 were also reflected in their sample outputs and in the observations or feedback from their paper adviser, where their writings were enhanced, making their texts easy to understand, with the aid of Grammarly.

The results validated Fahmi & Cahyono’s (2021) research findings that Grammarly provides comprehensive and beneficial feedback, such as corrections and suggestions to make the writing clearer, more precise, more effective, more readable, mistake-free, and impactful, with a high rate of accuracy and evaluation speed.

With these responses, it can be interpreted that Grammarly has a feature to make the text more precise and readable. Even so, double-checking the suggestions would help make the text easier to understand or maintain its readability.

The phenomenon was anchored on the theoretical framework of the Information Processing Theory of George Miller (1956). Although Grammarly provides useful feedback or suggestions, there are still specific faults that the program cannot catch and some misleading feedback (Wardatin et al., 2022). Thus, processing the suggestions or feedback is necessary to identify relevant and accurate suggestions and disregard irrelevant or inaccurate ones via selective attention. Only suggestions that fit the context and improve the text structure without changing the original meaning of the text are the only ones to be accepted.

It was evident from the above-mentioned theoretical framework that despite the usefulness and reliability of the tool, there are also times that it might suggest irrelevant ones. Thus, processing the suggestions should be taken into account to identify the only suggestions that would help a student in writing.

Conclusions

In line with the experiences of the participants in this analysis, the following conclusions are drawn:

The use of Grammarly contributes to the improvement of the writing performance of the campus writers. It makes them more confident to show off their articles without worrying about grammatical errors and the like.

Grammarly is only a helping tool that helps campus writers improve their grammatical accuracy and use of proper mechanics in writing. It is a reliable tool that they can use to polish their articles. Being too reliant on it is not advisable as it sometimes provides misleading feedback.

Since Grammarly is still an AI tool, there's always a chance for it to provide misleading feedback or suggestions. Therefore, comprehensively reviewing the suggestions is a big help to avoid deviating from the original meaning of the text.

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